

Strengthening Immunity: The Role of Nutrition in Preventing Viral Infections

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Abstract

Viral infections, such as COVID-19, can be highly contagious and easily transmitted, leading to widespread epidemics. While personal hygiene and social distancing remain the most effective strategies for preventing the transmission of viruses, boosting one's immunity through a balanced diet rich in essential nutrients can also play a significant role in protecting against viral infections. Research indicates that foods containing various bioactive compounds have demonstrated therapeutic potential against viral activity and can enhance the immune response in individuals. This article emphasizes the importance of strengthening immunity through proper nutrition as a proactive measure to prevent viral infections, highlighting key foods that serve as valuable candidates for improving immune function. Additionally, it is crucial to recognize that a holistic approach—one that encompasses not only diet but also regular physical activity, adequate sleep, and stress management—can further enhance immune resilience. Future investigations should explore how specific dietary patterns, such as the Mediterranean diet or plant-based eating, may impact immune health and viral resistance. By integrating nutrition with other health-promoting behaviors, individuals can better equip themselves to withstand viral threats.

Keywords: Infection, Virus, Bioactive compounds, Immune system, Nutrition.

1. Introduction

Many viral infections are highly contagious and easily transmissible, leading to widespread health problems and even death worldwide. Emerging viral infections are caused by various viruses, including measles, HIV, and influenza. Additionally, viruses such as SARS (Severe Acute Respiratory Syndrome) and MERS (Middle East Respiratory Syndrome), which cause respiratory diseases, have also emerged in recent years. The Spanish flu outbreak, caused by the H1N1 influenza virus at the beginning of the 20th century, was one of the deadliest pandemics in human history, according to the CDC and WHO. More recently, the outbreak of COVID-19, caused by the novel coronavirus SARS-CoV-2, was declared a pandemic by the WHO in March 2020. Studies on COVID-19 indicate that these viruses are primarily associated with two common types of transmission between humans and animals. They originate in animals and can be transmitted from animals to humans, as well as from human to human [1].

Despite the wide range of antiviral drugs currently available for potential treatment, the sudden emergence of new viral strains complicates the timely introduction of effective medications or therapies. Therefore, the most effective strategies for preventing transmissible infections include maintaining personal hygiene, practicing social distancing, and strengthening immunity against targeted viruses. By focusing on these preventive measures, individuals can better protect themselves and their communities from the threat of viral infections. To strengthen one's immunity, it is crucial to consume the right foods that contribute to a balanced and nutritious diet. Foods containing bioactive compounds—such as vitamins, minerals, fatty acids, polysaccharides, and non-nutritive substances like polyphenols—can be particularly beneficial due to their therapeutic functions. These compounds have the potential to directly counteract viruses or enhance the body's immune response. For instance, vitamins A, C, D, and E are known to play vital roles in the body's growth and repair mechanisms, contributing significantly to immune functionality [2].

Research indicates that consuming foods rich in these vitamins—including carrots, vegetables, fruit juices, sprout oils, nuts, seeds, milk, and dairy products—can effectively strengthen the immune system. A study on the effects of riboflavin against the MERS strain EMC demonstrated a logarithmic reduction of 7.4 in viral growth [3]. Additionally, vitamin D serves an important role as an immune modulator against the hepatitis C virus. Most vitamins function as strong antioxidants, which help eliminate free radicals and reduce oxidative stress within the body. Moreover, the ability of vitamin C to lessen the severity of respiratory infections caused by coronaviruses, including SARS, has been documented [4,5].

Lipids, especially polyunsaturated fatty acids (PUFAs) and a select group of medium-chain fatty acids, are recognized as potent antiviral agents. PUFAs have exhibited antiviral activity against hepatitis C virus and participate in regular physiological functions. Certain non-nutritive components, particularly phytochemicals like lignans, have also demonstrated significant antiviral properties due to their antioxidant, antiviral, and anti-inflammatory activities. Polyphenols, in particular, exhibit important antiviral activity against several viruses [6].

Given that the discovery of antiviral drugs for emerging viruses involves a lengthy process—including laboratory analyses and clinical trials—the use of existing dietary options to combat viruses is an appealing strategy. Strengthening the body's immunity through the consumption of nutrient-rich foods and bioactive compounds presents a promising solution, especially in the context of viral outbreaks. Researchers have comprehensively discussed the potential impact of a diverse array of bioactive compounds in foods on immunity against viruses, underscoring the importance of nutrition as a frontline defense.

2. Nutrients with Antiviral Properties

The rapid changes in lifestyle and socio-economic conditions have adversely affected public health, making a balanced diet a critical factor in strengthening immunity to combat diseases. Micronutrients play a vital role in this process. For instance, vitamins A, C, D, and E, along with trace minerals like iron, zinc, and selenium, have been shown to significantly modulate immune system function, serving as preventive measures against various diseases [7].

Vitamin A is essential for maintaining the integrity of mucosal surfaces, which act as barriers against pathogens. Vitamin C is a powerful antioxidant that enhances the production of white blood cells, crucial for fighting infections. Vitamin D has been linked to the regulation of immune responses and may reduce the risk of respiratory infections. Vitamin E also supports immune function by acting as an antioxidant, protecting cells from oxidative damage. Trace minerals such as zinc are fundamental for the development and function of immune cells, while selenium plays a crucial role in enhancing the body's antiviral defenses. Research has shown that deficiencies in these micronutrients can lead to increased susceptibility to infections and a higher risk of chronic diseases. Incorporating a variety of nutrient-dense foods into the daily diet—such as fruits, vegetables, nuts, and seeds—can help ensure adequate intake of these essential vitamins and minerals.

This dietary approach not only fortifies the immune system but also promotes overall health and well-being.

2.1. Polysaccharides

Polysaccharides are macromolecules with high molecular weights that perform essential functions in various physiological processes. These complex carbohydrates are composed of long chains of monosaccharides linked together through glycosidic bonds, which can be classified into two main types: homopolysaccharides and heteropolysaccharides. Notable examples of polysaccharides include cellulose, glycogen, and starch, which serve as primary energy reservoirs in both plants and animals. In addition to their nutritional importance, polysaccharides possess several therapeutic properties, such as antiviral, antioxidant, anticancer, and immune-modulating activities [8].

Numerous studies have demonstrated that polysaccharides, either alone or in combination with proteins and phenolic compounds, showcase significant medicinal effects. For example, a study conducted in 2018 reported that various polysaccharides—both natural and modified—exhibited antiviral properties against the influenza virus, human immunodeficiency virus (HIV), hepatitis virus, and herpes simplex virus [9].

Beta-glucan, a soluble food polysaccharide composed of beta-glucose linkages, is predominantly found in the cell walls of cereals. Research has linked beta-glucan to anti-cholesterolemic activity, contributing to heart health. This polysaccharide can inhibit and disrupt viral particles directly or enhance host immunity indirectly. Studies have shown that beta-glucan stimulates the production of cytokines and activates natural killer cells, T lymphocytes, and dendritic cells, ultimately strengthening the body's immune response. Notably, it was reported in 2020 that beta-glucan demonstrated effectiveness against HIV infections [10].

Fructans are another significant group of polysaccharides with antiviral properties, comprising chains of fructose molecules. Notable fructans, such as inulin and fructo-oligosaccharides, have been shown to enhance immune function and overall health. Common dietary sources of fructans include garlic, onion, chicory, and bananas. Research indicates that fructans can stimulate the activity of immune cells via Toll-like receptors (TLRs), which serve as a crucial first line of defense against bacterial and viral infections in innate immune cells, particularly natural killer cells [11].

Overall, the therapeutic potential of polysaccharides underscores their importance not only as dietary components but also as functional ingredients that can positively impact health and immunity. Polysaccharides that are substituted with sulfate groups can exhibit various antiviral and therapeutic properties. The effectiveness of sulfated polysaccharides is highly dependent on the degree of substitution, as well as the position and type of glycosidic bonds present within their structure. Significant sources of sulfated polysaccharides include various medicinal plants, as well as edible and wild mushrooms, and certain types of seaweed. Among the sulfated polysaccharides identified to have antiviral properties are fucoidan, galactan, carrageenan,

ramnan, olvan, and galactofucan. These compounds have been reported to demonstrate antiviral effects against several viruses, including hepatitis, influenza, herpes simplex virus, and HIV [12]. Sulfated polysaccharides achieve their antiviral action by interacting with the viral envelope, thereby inhibiting the processes of virus absorption and penetration into host cells.

2.2. Proteins

Lectins and electoferrin are notable proteins with antiviral properties that interfere with virus replication. Lectins serve as valuable tools for analyzing the interactions and surface functions of biological molecules within cells [13].

These proteins can recognize specific viruses and bind irreversibly to sugars through their binding sites. They exhibit effectiveness against various viruses, including HIV, influenza, hepatitis C virus, and coronaviruses. Notably, most mannose-binding lectins have demonstrated antiviral effects specifically against coronaviruses. Lectins primarily target viral envelopes by binding to unique carbohydrate structures, such as glycoproteins and high-mannose glycans. They serve as potent inhibitors of HIV by interacting with glycosylated moieties on the surface of cells, thereby limiting the conformational changes required for viral binding. Lectins have a strong affinity for viral glycoproteins, particularly gp120 and gp41, which are present in the HIV envelope. Lactoferrin, another important protein, is an iron-containing glycoprotein commonly found in mammalian milk, often referred to as "red milk protein." The concentration of lactoferrin varies among different types of milk and is influenced by the stage of lactation. This protein plays a crucial role in innate immunity and is considered a first-line defense mechanism against several infections. Lactoferrin exhibits antimicrobial, anti-inflammatory, and immunomodulatory properties, which are particularly beneficial for protecting infants. It modulates immune responses by increasing cytokine production, promoting the maturation of helper T cells, and facilitating the elimination of intracellular reactive oxygen species. Lactoferrin has been shown to be effective against various viruses, including adenovirus, poliovirus, herpes simplex virus (HSV), HIV, influenza virus, and hepatitis viruses. Additionally, the iron in lactoferrin acts as an antioxidant, helping to neutralize harmful reactive oxygen species generated within cells. Overall, both lectins and lactoferrin exemplify the significant role of proteins in enhancing antiviral immunity and serve as potential therapeutic agents in the fight against viral infections.

2.3. Lipids

During viral infections, fatty acids are essential for the replication of viruses. However, certain fatty acids possess the ability to inactivate microbes (either directly or indirectly) and enhance immune responses. For instance, omega-3 fatty acids, which are abundant in fish oil, serve as endogenous compounds that bolster immunity against infections such as hepatitis C virus, COVID-19, SARS, and MERS. Unsaturated fatty acids, particularly polyunsaturated fatty acids (PUFAs), can directly target microbial cell walls, leading to membrane destabilization and lysis. This process not only increases the release of bioactive metabolites, such as prostaglandins but also helps to prevent viral

replication. The metabolites of omega-3 fatty acids have been identified as having immune-regulating functions and are referred to as intermediate compounds in this context. Bioactive lipids exhibit significant antiviral properties, especially against enveloped viruses. They also function as anti-inflammatory and antimicrobial agents, playing a vital role in supporting the immune system.

2.4. Vitamins

Vitamins are essential for normal health, immunity, energy production and some key functions in the body. Vitamins are essential micronutrients that the body cannot produce by itself, except for vitamin D, and must be obtained through food. Vitamin A is a group of fat-soluble vitamins that are necessary for growth, development, eyesight and immunity. The clinical use of vitamin A in the treatment of several infectious diseases as an anti-inflammatory agent has been reported. There are several active forms of vitamin A such as retinol, retinal and retinoic acid. A group of carotenoids, especially beta-carotene, called pro-vitamin A, is converted into retinol in the human intestine and absorbed in the body. Among the different forms of vitamin A, retinoic acid has the most bioactive structure. Retinoic acid can increase the production of anti-inflammatory cytokines and protective IgA antibodies against viral infections such as measles and affect A viruses [14].

Vitamin A deficiency causes excessive inflammation and makes you more susceptible to viral infection. In addition, retinoic acid depletion is a common phenomenon during inflammatory diseases such as covid-19, where immune system collapse is observed by limiting the type 1 interferon synthesis pathway. Vitamin A can reduce the mortality rate in children infected with the virus and is recommended for the treatment of measles. It has been reported in a study that the administration of vitamin A can reduce the rate of complications among HIV-infected children [17,16,15]. Since the HIV virus stops the immune function of infected people and makes them susceptible to other infections, vitamin A can play an important role by increasing immunity. Most reports have concluded that vitamin A supplementation can enhance immunity in virus-infected individuals by targeting T cells and B cell function [18].

Vitamin D regulates the expression of antimicrobial peptides and serves as a primary regulator of the intracellular signaling pathway and viral gene transcription [19]. The overproduction of dihydroxyvitamin D supports the synthesis of antimicrobial peptides, specifically cathelicidin, which can act as potent antiviral agents. Cathelicidins are small molecules produced mainly by leukocytes and epithelial cells and possess anti-inflammatory properties. They exhibit chemotactic activity and inhibit viral proliferation. Vitamin E is a powerful antioxidant that enhances immune function. This vitamin acts as a free radical scavenger within cell membranes, functioning as a PUFA chain breaker by absorbing peroxy lipid radicals and thereby preventing the oxidation of adjacent fatty acid chains [20]. Research has shown that while several antioxidants have been tested against the influenza virus, vitamin E exhibited the highest efficacy in inhibiting these target viruses. Additionally, studies have highlighted the functions of vitamins C and E as antioxidant

and anti-inflammatory agents, making them suitable options for the treatment of COVID-19.

Vitamin C is a water-soluble vitamin naturally present in various foods, especially fruits and vegetables. It is a strong antioxidant that can enhance the body's immune response. Numerous clinical studies have demonstrated that vitamin C intake increases resistance to many viral and bacterial infections. Specifically, vitamin C has been shown to be beneficial during upper respiratory tract infections and severe pneumonia. Reports indicate that respiratory syncytial virus (RSV), which causes common lower and upper respiratory infections, generates reactive oxygen species (ROS) in the epithelial cells of the lungs. The accumulation of ROS, due to the inhibition of lung antioxidants, can lead to pulmonary toxicity, while the administration of vitamin C has been found to reduce viral infection rates [21]. Furthermore, vitamin C enhances the response of immune system cells and can decrease the severity of colds and respiratory infections. It also increases the production of interferon β/α , an important factor for antiviral immunity during infections.

2.5. Minerals

Numerous studies have explored the role of trace elements in maintaining and strengthening immunity, thereby reducing the risk of infection. Reports indicate that trace elements can act as barriers against infection through several layers of immunity, including physical and chemical barriers. Additionally, these elements function as antioxidants, facilitating the adaptation of the immune system, enhancing innate immunity, and promoting antibody production. Furthermore, several minerals serve as cofactors for enzymes that play critical roles in immune function [22].

Zinc is an important mineral for innate immunity, playing a crucial role in the activity of natural killer cells, cytokine release, and antibody production. It enhances the activity of natural killer cells, increases the phagocytic capacity of monocytes, and contributes to the production of interferons. Zinc regulates the function of various immune cells, including macrophages, neutrophils, and B cells [22].

Additionally, zinc is a component of several antiviral enzymes, such as proteases and polymerases. It acts as a cofactor for antioxidant enzymes, including superoxide dismutase, and is involved in the synthesis of metallothionein, a cysteine-rich protein that protects cells from free radicals and supports cellular immunity. Zinc has been shown to reduce the incidence of upper respiratory tract infections, such as pneumonia and rhinovirus infections, as well as cold viruses, including influenza virus, hepatitis C virus, human papillomavirus, HIV, and herpes simplex virus. Furthermore, its antiviral properties can help reduce inflammation, and T cell-mediated immunity underscores its importance in maintaining immunity and effectively treating viral infections [23].

The mineral element copper has long been used as an antiseptic, antibacterial, and antiviral agent. Due to its unpaired free electron in outer orbitals, copper ions can participate in oxidation-reduction reactions. These ions create holes in viral membranes

and produce free radicals, which can lead to the destruction of genetic material.

Studies have examined the mechanism of antiviral action of copper ions against herpes simplex virus and have shown that the formation of free radicals by copper ions causes oxidative damage to biomolecules. Copper plays a role in the function of macrophages, neutrophils, and monocytes, and it can enhance the activity of natural killer cells. Copper has been found to be effective against several viruses, including influenza viruses and noroviruses. Selenium is a key factor in several biological processes, such as enhancing immunity, inhibiting free radicals, protecting against oxidative stress, promoting cell differentiation, and maintaining antibody levels. Research has shown that oxidative stress caused by viral infections is characterized by the production of reactive oxygen species (ROS) that can be harmful to cells. The antioxidant activity and free radical inhibition of selenium are attributed to selenoprotein enzymes containing selenocysteine, such as glutathione peroxidase, glutathione reductase, selenoprotein P, and thioredoxin reductase. Some functions of selenoproteins include antioxidant activity, redox regulation, effects on leukocytes, and the production of natural killer cells and interferon [22].

It has been reported that selenium supplementation is effective against HIV, hepatitis, and influenza A viruses. Iron is an important trace element in the immune system, required for protein synthesis, DNA synthesis and repair, cellular respiration, cell proliferation, lymphocyte maturation, and the regulation of gene expression [24].

Through the Fenton reaction, iron produces hydroxyl radicals that can damage DNA, lipids, and proteins, highlighting the importance of iron homeostasis. Iron plays a crucial role in the proliferation of T cells, the differentiation and regulation between T helper (Th) cells and cytotoxic T cells, as well as the production and activity of cytokines. It has been shown that iron is essential for viral replication and that there is competition for iron between the host and the virus. Excess intake or high serum iron levels can be harmful and are associated with infections, particularly with the hepatitis B virus.

The bioavailability of bioactive compounds released from the food matrix is also important for host cell metabolism after digestion. The most commonly used methods for assessing bioavailability include *in vitro* studies of simulated gastrointestinal digestion. The bioavailability of different nutrients can vary between macronutrients and micronutrients [25].

Several factors influence nutrient absorption, including external factors (such as the structure of food matrices, the form of nutrients, combinations with other nutrients, and the presence of non-nutrient components) and internal factors (such as age, sex, physiological status, and nutritional status). Generally, the bioavailability of macronutrients, such as carbohydrates, proteins, and lipids, is high, often around 90%. In contrast, the bioavailability of minerals can range from 1% to 90%, indicating significant variability.

3. Conclusion

Nutrients play a vital role in maintaining the normal physiology and health of the human body and are essential for immunity and the fight against infections. A select group of nutrients, including sulfated polysaccharides, electrophorin, vitamins, and minerals, can interact directly with viruses or indirectly activate cells involved in both the innate and adaptive immune systems.

Evidence has shown that certain nutrients bind to cell surface receptors on immune cells, inducing several signaling pathways that regulate immune responses. The immunomodulatory function of these nutrients can enhance immunity by modulating the activity of macrophages, promoting anti-inflammatory responses, and facilitating the action of lipids and their bioactive metabolites against enveloped viruses such as HIV and HCV. Minerals also play a crucial role in the function of immune cells, including macrophages and neutrophils, as well as dendritic cells derived from interleukins, which are essential for the production of interferon-gamma. These processes are critical for activating natural killer (NK) cells to combat viral infections through specific signaling pathways.

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In critical situations, such as during the COVID-19 pandemic, where there is a lack of effective antiviral drugs against new viruses, strengthening immunity through a well-balanced diet rich in macronutrients and micronutrients emerges as one of the most practical preventive measures against viral infections. A healthy, balanced diet complemented by nutritional supplements is necessary to maintain optimal immune system function.

The immune system is often compromised during infections and disease processes; thus, consuming plenty of fresh fruits, green vegetables, and foods rich in antioxidants is beneficial in combating viral infections. Additionally, it is essential to avoid processed and unhealthy foods that may contribute to inflammation and weaken immune response.

Bioactive food compounds significantly contribute to the effective functioning of the immune system, providing protection against viral and other infections. These compounds may be considered as preventive agents against viral pathogens and can support overall health.

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